

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Modified urea forms evaluated in lowland rice

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The main reason for low efficiency of urea N—which generally does not exceed 50%—is due to loss of N through one or more of the well-known channels: runoff, leaching, denitrification, and volatilization. Several modified and coated urea fertilizers have been developed in recent years. We evaluated three of these, Mussorie rock phosphate-coated urea (MRPU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and large granulated urea (LGU) (6-8 mm diam), against prilled urea (PU) during 1991 and 1992 wet seasons (WS).

The soil was alluvial (Inceptisol) and sandy loam in texture with a pH of 6.8, CEC 16.3 meq/100 g soil, total N 0.05%, available P 36 ppm, and exchangeable K 1 meq/100 g soil. The water level in the field ranged from 5 to 15 cm during the crop growth period.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of variety Gayataru (CR1018) were planted during the first fortnight of July at a spacing of 15 x 15 cm. All the urea fertilizers were broadcast, applied

basally, or applied in two or three splits (see table). The N level was maintained at 60 kg/ha in the 10 treatments which were replicated three times in a randomized block design.

When the entire N dose was applied basally, MRPU and NCU were superior to PU and LGU in grain yield (see table). Single basal applications of MRPU and NCU were comparable to PU when applied in two and three splits in 1991 and three splits in 1992. A two-way split application of MRPU or NCU was not better than a single basal application. Applying LGU in two splits was comparable to applying PU in two splits. A three-way split of PU had an advantage over a two-way split in 1992 only.

N use efficiency across treatments showed a similar trend. All N applications increased grain yield significantly over the no-N control, up to 54% in 1991 and 39% in 1992.

Panicle number was highest with a basal application of MRPU in 1991; all N application treatments, except basal applications of PU and LGU, were comparable to it. In 1992, the most panicles were recorded in the conventional three-way split application of PU; all N application treatments were

comparable to it except basal application of PU and LGU. The highest panicle weight was recorded under the NCU two-way split application in 1991; comparable to it were basal applications of MRPU, LGU, and NCU and the three-way split application of PU. During 1992, highest panicle weight was recorded with PU. ■

Fertilizer scheduling and economics of varietal mixtures of rice

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Cultivating mixtures of rice varieties is a prevalent practice in many rice-growing regions. In this system, seeds of a photoperiod-insensitive variety and a photoperiod-sensitive variety are sown as a mixture in a 70-30 (wt/wt) ratio at the beginning of the wet season (WS). The varieties are successively harvested at the end of the WS and dry season (DS). We evaluated the fertilizer requirements to determine the economic productivity of the system.

The experiment was conducted during 1988-90 WS and DS. The soil at the site is lateritic loam, acidic, and of medium fertility. Aryan (Ptbl) for WS and Chettadi (local) for DS were the varieties in the mixture. The treatments were combinations of the recommended fertilizer schedule for a single variety (40-20-20 kg NPK/ha) applied in three proportions (100,75, and 50%) for the WS crop and four proportions (100,75, 50, and 25%) for the DS crop, along with a control where varieties were cropped singly in the different seasons under the recommended fertilizer schedule.

Cropping the varieties singly recorded higher grain yield than did the mixture during individual seasons as well as annually. Grain yield of the varietal mixture did not vary by season, possibly because of the substantial organic matter buildup in the system. Lowering the nutrient supply to 50% or less significantly reduced grain yield during the DS, attributable to the increased mineralization of the large

Effect of different treatments on grain yield, yield attributes, and N use efficiency in rice. CRRRI, Cuttack, India. 1991-92 WS.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Panicles/m ² (no.)		Panicle weight (g)		N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N)	
	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992
Control	4.0	4.1	245	223	2.22	2.15	-	-
PU, all basal	5.3	5.2	279	258	2.24	2.25	22.2	17.3
MRPU, all basal	5.9	5.6	297	282	2.30	2.35	32.5	24.3
LGU, all basal	5.3	5.2	281	265	2.21	2.27	22.5	17.3
NCU, all basal	5.9	5.5	291	285	2.33	2.32	31.3	23.3
PU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI) ^b	5.9	5.4	292	266	2.67	2.58	31.3	21.8
MRPU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI)	6.1	5.7	292	283	2.69	2.50	36.0	26.8
LGU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI)	5.9	5.5	290	276	2.66	2.50	31.3	22.3
NCU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI)	6.1	5.8	291	284	2.71	2.52	35.2	27.0
PU, 3 splits (1/2 basal + 1/4 21 DT ^c + 1/4 PI)	6.1	5.8	293	286	2.66	2.55	35.7	27.2
LSD (P=0.05)	0.3	0.2	15	20	0.20	0.27		

^aN content in fertilizers: MRPU = 36%; PU, LGU, and NCU = 46%. ^bPI = panicle initiation. ^cDT = days after transplanting.

Grain yield of rice under varietal mixtures and economics. Kerala, India.

Fertilizer schedule (% of recommended dose) ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)			Economics			
WS	DS	WS	DS	Annual	Total income (\$/ha)	Total cost (\$/ha)	Profit (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
<i>For varietal mixtures</i>								
100	100	2.4	2.5	4.9	726	497	229	1.46
100	75	2.2	2.5	4.7	703	494	209	1.42
100	50	2.3	2.5	4.8	716	489	227	1.46
100	25	2.4	2.3	4.7	712	485	227	1.47
75	100	2.4	2.5	4.9	733	494	239	1.48
75	75	2.3	2.6	4.9	728	491	237	1.48
75	50	2.1	2.2	4.3	657	486	171	1.35
75	25	2.3	2.1	4.4	679	482	197	1.41
50	100	2.3	2.5	4.8	715	489	226	1.46
50	75	2.3	2.6	4.9	728	486	242	1.50
50	50	2.3	2.2	4.5	678	482	196	1.41
50	25	2.2	2.2	4.4	679	478	201	1.42
<i>For single variety</i>								
100	100	2.9	2.7	5.6	747	636	111	1.17
LSD (0.05)		ns ^b	0.3	0.4			-	-

^aRecommended fertilizer schedule was 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha. ^b = not significant.

quantities of crop residue leftover from the WS crop under high N levels.

With regard to annual yield, the 50% WS: 75% DS treatment yielded about the

same as the treatments receiving 100% or 75% in either season. A net savings of 30-15-15 kg NPK/ha occurred, which is 75% of the dose for a single season, by

Residual effects of P on wheat in a rice - wheat sequence

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We assessed the residual effects of fertilizer P sources applied to rice on subsequent wheat growth. The soil was a loamy sand with pH 5.1. 0.59% organic C, 90.96 mg available N/kg (extracted in 0.32% KMnO₄), 3.39 mg available P/kg (Bray I), and 20.45 mg available K/kg (extracted in neutral 1 N NH₄OA₂).

Residual effects of different sources and levels of P applied to rice on subsequent wheat growth.

Treatment	P uptake (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Absolute agronomic efficiency ^a
Control (0 kg P/ha)	3.03	0.8	1.9	-
<i>Sources</i>				
SSP	4.25	0.96	1.99	-
DAP	4.22	0.98	2.00	-
MRP	6.02	1.05	2.02	-
PRP	5.74	1.04	2.01	-
LSD (0.05)	0.75	0.02	0.03	-
<i>P level (kg/ha)</i>				
13.1	4.41	0.96	1.94	10.69
26.2	5.09	1.01	2.00	7.25
39.3	5.68	1.05	2.08	5.95
17.5 kg P applied to wheat	11.97	1.46	2.4	36.57
LSD (0.05)	0.85	0.02	0.04	

^aIncrease in grain yield over control/kg P applied.

cropping varietal mixtures when compared with monocropping.

Cultivating a single variety recorded a narrow increase in annual gross income over varietal mixtures (see table). This was not, however, commensurate with the larger increase in production costs for cultivating single varieties. Savings in cultivation costs of \$139-158 were obtained with varietal mixtures compared with single cultivation.

The system may bring down production costs substantially because the DS crop requires no expenditure for field preparation and transplanting. The reduced production cost contributes to a significantly higher net income and benefit-cost (B-C) ratio with varietal mixtures over a single-cropped variety.

Among the fertilizer levels for the varietal mixture, the 50:75 schedule recorded the maximum net income and B-C ratio. This treatment increased the net income to \$13 over the 100:100 schedule varietal mixture and \$131 over the single variety. ■

We applied 13.1, 26.2, and 39.3 kg P/ha to the rice as either single super-phosphate (SSP) or diammonium phosphate (DAP) at transplanting, or mussorie rock phosphate (MRP) or purulia rock phosphate (PRP) 15 d before transplanting; we also applied 175 kg P/ha as SSP to the wheat at sowing. Both rice and wheat also received 40 kg N/ha and 16.6 kg K/ha. Treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design. Rice variety Culture 1 and wheat variety Sonalika were used. Wheat was sown at 120 kg seed/ha at a planting depth of 5 cm in rows 20 cm apart.

Significant differences were observed among both sources and levels of P in their residual effects on P uptake and to a lesser extent on grain yield (see table). Differences among sources were greater than those among levels, with the rock phosphates having the greatest residual effect. In no case did the residual effects match the benefit of directly applying P to the wheat. ■